

FORMING A SENSE OF TOLERANCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation. For primary school, the problem of tolerance itself is relevant. The absence of this quality in people inevitably leads to conflicts both at the country level and in interpersonal relations. In these circumstances, it is extremely important to educate tolerance among the younger generation, since the adoption of the principles and norms of tolerance is an important condition for mutual understanding between people, interaction, harmony, and cohesion of society. Only a tolerant person can exist in modern conditions, which are characterized by constant changes associated with the need to adapt to them.

Key words: tolerance, junior schoolchild, elementary school, social environment.

Аннотация. Для начальной школы проблема толерантности сама по себе является актуальной. Отсутствие данного качества у людей неминуемо приводит к конфликтам как на уровне страны, так и в межличностных отношениях. В этих обстоятельствах чрезвычайно важно воспитывать толерантность у молодого поколения, так как принятие принципов и норм толерантности – это важное условие взаимопонимания между людьми, взаимодействия, согласия, сплочения общества. Только толерантная личность сможет существовать в современных условиях, которым характерны постоянные изменения, связанные с необходимостью приспосабливаться к ним.

Ключевые слова: толерантность, младший школьник, начальная школа, социальная среда.

Introduction. Tolerance is an active moral position and psychological readiness for tolerance in the way of mutual understanding between peoples, social groups, positive relations with people of other cultural, national, religious or social environment.

Recently, there is more talk about a tolerant world, a world free of violence and cruelty, a world where the unique and inviolable human person is the main value.

The undoubted importance of this topic is confirmed by the existence of the International Day of Tolerance, which is celebrated on November 16, and the "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance" adopted by UNESCO. These social phenomena especially affect young people, who are characterized by maximalism, a desire to solve complex social problems "simple and fast" according to their age characteristics. Recent years have been characterized by a catastrophic increase in all types of antisocial behavior among youth and teenagers. The number of radical youth anti-social organizations that recruit inexperienced youth to extremist groups is increasing.

The question arises: at what age should the formation of tolerance begin?

In our opinion, the formation of tolerance is a long and complex process, which begins from the birth of children, continues in preschool and school childhood, and to some extent continues throughout life. This process is influenced by many factors, among which family and education are crucial. And if family members do not accept tolerance as their attitude, the child entering school will not be ready to accept other people as they are. But every year, the number of children from different nationalities, families with different social status, and financial opportunities is increasing in our school. And it is important for a primary school teacher to convey to each student the idea that different individual qualities of people only complement each other and make up a colorful and therefore beautiful world.

Tolerance should be cultivated from the first days of the child's arrival at school.

The main thing should be noted: the development of the child's spiritual potential, his creative abilities directly depends on the creation of an atmosphere of tolerance in the classroom.

Cultivation of a culture of tolerance should be carried out according to the following formula: parents + children + teacher.

Many people think that parenting is a one-way process of pouring "spiritual liquid" from one vessel to another. Such a one-sided approach to the ever-important problem of personal education would be far from complete. By nurturing the feelings of kindness and sensitivity in preschool children, students, and subordinates, we ourselves become kind and sensitive, increase diligence and responsibility towards ourselves and society, and cultivate these qualities in ourselves. .

On the other hand, if we are rude, irresponsible, all this is often inadvertently passed on to our children. Many examples from life can be given to confirm what has been said, which require deep scientific research. In all life situations, of course, in order to see the personality in a person in the future, it is necessary to think about the issues of education, personal development and be especially careful.

You should always remember: to educate - to think, to think - to educate. Naturally, at the current stage of the development of our society, special attention should be paid to developing such qualities as responsibility, nobility, politeness, hard work, and honesty in children.

The effect of the work is noticeable not only for eliminating shortcomings, but also for the development of positive qualities: respect for parents, hard work, kindness, honesty, the ability to make friends, etc. are inherited from them. Students should develop a desire to learn about the life of their ancestors: what they did (often reflected in their surnames), where they lived, what traditions they followed.

In the process of educational work, I set myself the following tasks:

- educating a person who understands human dignity;
- the education of tolerance (it is necessary to understand the high and useful principle of tolerance in itself: it does not mean tolerating evil and crime);
- humanitarian education;
- formation of the ability to resolve conflicts without violence.

Forming a tolerant attitude towards others in primary school is aimed at educating a young student's self-confidence, self-respect and respect for others.

It is difficult to overestimate the importance of stories in which children learn lessons and moral conclusions. By reading them, we draw the attention of children to good deeds and good deeds.

Cultivating a good relationship with classmates is helped by participation in joint activities of the class (competitions, games, contests that develop imagination). Both boys and girls are required to participate in all activities.

There are often conflicts in the classroom. The class leader should always emphasize the idea that any problem can be solved.

Methodical and game technique.

"Morning begins with a smile"

Every day, at the beginning of the first lesson, I invite the children to look at each other, say hello and smile (a great mood charge, and work goes well with such a charge)

"writing a letter"

Children write letters to each other, twice a week the postman delivers them to the recipients (this develops the ability and desire to communicate, for shy children it is better to express their feelings and thoughts on paper than verbally) easy)

"Friendly Wash"

Children stand in two rows very far from each other. One child passes between the rows (by "washing"), other children take turns shaking his hand, patting him on the back in a friendly manner, while saying words of praise, sympathy, encouragement

(such "washing" , a bright, cheerful and happy child appears). It is recommended to "wash" 1-2 people a day.

"Anger"

Every child has the right to be sad. Together with the children, they developed the following rule (a way to get rid of frustration):

"Don't be angry, tell as soon as possible"

"Trash"

The teacher puts a small bucket in the middle of the class and invites the children to think. Why does a person need a litter box and why should it always be emptied? Then the children are invited to imagine life without a garbage can, when garbage gradually fills the rooms, it becomes difficult to breathe, move, people start to get sick. But also with emotions. Each of us accumulates emotions that often become unnecessary and useless. And some like to collect these feelings, for example, to collect their grievances or fears. I suggest children to throw unnecessary resentment, anger, fear into the "trash bin". To do this, children write down on paper the feelings they want to get rid of, for example: "I am sad ...", "I am angry with ...", "I am afraid ... ". Then they tear the leaves into pieces, throw them in the trash, and the attendant takes this bucket to the trash can (thus, children learn to cope with feelings of sadness, anger)

"Surprise for the winner"

A child who has won any competition will be doubly happy if his classmates congratulate him from the bottom of his heart. We will certainly come up with a concert number for this child and perform it.

Tolerance means caring for all life on our planet, fighting violence together, understanding each other and building a peaceful future.

List of references

1. Grevtseva Class IV lesson "What is tolerance?" // Head of the class. - 2006. - No. 4. - P. 81-88.
2. Кудайбергенова, У. К., & Мамбетуллаева, С. М. (2014). Роль экологических факторов в формировании заболеваемости населения Каракалпакстана. *Austrian Journal of Technical and Natural Sciences*, (1-2), 3-7.
3. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2012). РИСК РАЗВИТИЯ АЛЛЕРГОПАТОЛОГИИ У НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН. *Актуальные проблемы современной науки*, (6), 344-346.
4. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2012). АНАЛИЗ НОЗОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ СТРУКТУРЫ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН МЕТОДОМ МНОГОФАКТОРНОЙ НЕЛИНЕЙНОЙ КОРРЕЛЯЦИИ. *Аспирант и соискатель*, (2), 94-96.

5. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2020). ГЕОГРАФИЧЕСКИЕ, ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ, СТРУКТУРНЫЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ И СВЯЗАННЫЕ С НИМИ БОЛЕЗНИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ЮЖНОГО ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. Евразийский Союз Ученых, (12-2 (81)), 12-13.

6. Кудайбергенова, У., & Бегжанов, М. (2022). стажер-исследователь. Доктор экономических наук, профессор ЮВ Федорова Доктор филологических наук, профессор АА Зарайский Доктор социологических наук, доцент ТВ Смирнова, 35.

7. Матмуратова, Г., Кудайбергенова, У., & Бегжанов, М. (2022). БИОЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ЖУКОВ-ЛИСТОЕДОВ (COLEOPTERA: CHRYSOMELIDAE) ЮЖНОГО ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. In СОВРЕМЕННАЯ НАУЧНАЯ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТЬ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА (pp. 35-39).

8. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2022). К ВОПРОСУ ВЛИЯНИЯ АНТРОПОГЕННЫХ ФАКТОРОВ НА СОСТОЯНИЕ БИОРАЗНООБРАЗИЯ НАЦИОНАЛЬНОГО ПАРКА «ЮЖНЫЙ УСТЮРТ» В ПРИАРАЛЬЕ. ББК 72 А43 А43 АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ НАУКИ И ТЕХНИКИ/Сборник трудов по материалам VIII Международного конкурса научно-исследовательских работ (15 апреля).

9. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2021). НЕКОТОРЫЕ АСПЕКТЫ ВЫЯВЛЕНИЯ ФАКТОРОВ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО РИСКА ДЛЯ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ РЕГИОНА ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. Ответственный редактор: Сукиасян Асатур Альбертович, кандидат экономических наук, доцент. В состав редакционной коллегии и организационного комитета входят: Алиев Закир Гусейн оглы, доктор философии аграрных наук, 14.

10. Кудайбергенова, У. К., Жаксиликова, С. Б., & Айимбетова, Р. Б. (2021). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ЗАГРЯЗНЯЮЩИХ ВЕЩЕСТВ АТМОСФЕРЫ В РАЗЛИЧНЫХ РАЙОНАХ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН. In Advances in Science and Technology (pp. 23-24).

11. Кудайбергенова, У. К., & Матмуратова, Г. И. (2021). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ РАНЖИРОВАНИЕ ТЕРРИТОРИИ РЕГИОНА ЮЖНОГО ПРИАРАЛЬЯ ПО СТЕПЕНИ ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЯ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ. In Advances in Science and Technology (pp. 25-26).

12. Кудайбергенова, У. К., & Матмуратова, Г. И. (2020). ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЗАГРЯЗНЕНИЯ АТМОСФЕРНОГО ВОЗДУХА НА СОСТОЯНИЕ ЗДОРОВЬЯ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ ПРИАРАЛЬЯ. Форум молодых ученых, (6), 365-367.

13. Кудайбергенова, У. К., & Матмуратова, Г. (2014). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ УСЛОВИЯ КАК ФАКТОР РИСКА РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЯ

АЛЛЕРГИЧЕСКИХ ЗАБОЛЕВАНИЙ В КАРАКАЛПАКСТАНЕ. The Way of Science, 13.

14. Кудайбергенова, У. К., & Мамбетуллаева, С. М. (2019). Экологическая безопасность и ранжирование районов Республики Каракалпакстан по плотности загрязнения. In Итоги и перспективы развития агропромышленного комплекса (pp. 395-399).

15. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2017). РОЛЬ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ФАКТОРОВ В ФОРМИРОВАНИИ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ НАСЕЛЕНИЯ РЕСПУБЛИКИ КАРАКАЛПАКСТАН. Форум молодых ученых, (4 (8)), 328-330.

16. Кудайбергенова, У. К. (2015). Экологические факторы роста распространенности аллергопатологии в Южном Приаралье. In Современные тенденции в научной деятельности (pp. 785-789).

17. Матмуратова, Г., Кудайбергенова, У., & Бегжанов, М. ПУТЬ НАУКИ. ПУТЬ НАУКИ Учредители: Издательство «Научное обозрение», (4), 11-13.

18. Axtamovna, M. A. (2022). The Formation of Artistic Pictures of the World of Literary Works. EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION, 2(1), 151-153.

19. Axtamovna, M. A. (2021). LITERARY ANALYSIS OF THE WORK OF M. MITCHELL "GONE WITH THE WIND". ResearchJet Journal of Analysis and Inventions, 2(6), 1-6.

20. Aziza Axtamovna Marupova. (2023). LINGUOPOETIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ARTISTIC TEXT. International Journal Of Literature And Languages, 3(05), 83–86. <https://doi.org/10.37547/ijll/Volume03Issue05-17>

21. Sharopova, F., & Marupova, A. (2023). GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE OBJECT AS A MEMBER OF THE SENTENCE IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK. Академические исследования в современной науке, 2(5), 198-201.

22. Sharopova FR, Marupova AA. COMPARATIVE RESEARCH OF INDIRECT OBJECT IN THE ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES. YOUTH, SCIENCE, EDUCATION: TOPICAL ISSUES, ACHIEVEMENTS AND INNOVATIONS. 2022 Nov 5;1(6):136-40.

23. Marupova, A. A. (2022, April). EXPRESSIVENESS AND EVALUATIVENESS OF METAPHOR IN THE NOVEL OF M. MITCHELL'S "GONE WITH THE WIND". In International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics (pp. 136-139).

24. Marupova, A. A. (2021). LINGUOPOETIC MEANS AND WAYS OF INTRODUCING THE IMAGE OF THE MAIN CHARACTER IN M. MITCHELLS NOVEL "GONE WITH THE WIND". Theoretical & Applied Science, (8), 313-317.

25. Марупова Азиза Ахтамовна (2020). Motivation in the formation of professional and communicative competence of a student of a non-linguistic university. Евразийский научный журнал, (3), 50-52.
26. Марупова, А. А. (2016). СПОСОБЫ ВЫРАЖЕНИЯ ПРИБЛИЗИТЕЛЬНОГО КОЛИЧЕСТВА В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ. Ученый XXI века, (2-4).
27. Марупова, А. А. ОТРАЖЕНИЕ ВИРТУАЛЬНОЙ РЕАЛЬНОСТИ В РОМАНЕ “СКОТНЫЙ ДВОР” ОРУЭЛЛА. УЧЕНЫЙ XXI ВЕКА, 35.
28. Marupova, A. A. THE USE OF SOCIOLINGUISTIC TERMS IN THE THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL PREPARING OF PHILOLOGISTS.
29. Sanakulovna, A. N. (2021). The Use of the Innovative “Flipped Classroom” Model for the Organization of Independent Learning Activities of Students. European journal of innovation in nonformal education, 1(2), 76-78.
30. Sanakulovna, A. N. (2023). Incomplete Sentences with Zero Subjects. Web of Synergy: International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, 2(5), 576-580.
31. Artikova, N. S. (2022, May). IDENTIFYING QUALITATIVE SYNTAXEME. In International Conference on Research Identity, Value and Ethics (pp. 212-214).
32. Nodira, A. (2021). The flipped classroom. Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research, 2(05), 312-316.
33. Ибрагимов, Ш. Р., Шаматов, И. Я., & Исламов, Ш. Э. (2020). Особенности повреждений челюстей. Вопросы науки и образования, (30 (114)), 36-44.

